

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF NIGERIAN WOMEN REPRESENTATION IN MEDIA DISCOURSE

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Abstract

This study is set out to analyze the representations of Nigerian women in media discourse. The study particularly interrogates the ways in which media discourse serves as an avenue to construct female gender stereotypes and stigmatization in the society. Two selected newspapers namely: Daily trust and Vanguard were analyzed through Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) and semiotic frame works. It was argued that women representation ideologically reflects the existing power relations that affect women in the society. Thus, women representations in the selected newspapers are fed with gendered stereotypes and peripheral roles. Through the Prism of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), this study uncovers the underlying ideologies and power dynamics in media representations. The study concludes that there is a deeper understanding on how media shapes societal perceptions of gender and how it contributes to the reproduction of gender inequalities.

Keywords

Women, representation, media, stereotype, critical discourse analysis.

Introduction

This study is a critical analysis of women representation in media discourse, and reveals a persistent pattern of reinforcing societal gender stereotypes and power imbalances.

The representation of women in media discourse is a complex and multifaceted issue that reflects and shapes societal attitudes towards them. This analysis will examine the ways in which women are represented in media discourse,

highlighting the dominant themes, stereotypes, and power dynamics that shape these representations. This study draws illustrations from two representative Nigerian national dailies, Daily Trust and Vanguard newspapers, respectively.

Problem Statement

Despite advancements in gender equality and media development in Nigeria, the representation of women in media discourse remains largely stereotypical, marginal, and unbalanced. Women are often portrayed in passive, domestic, or hyper-sexualized roles, while their achievements, voices, and leadership contributions receive limited coverage. This reflects deeper societal power structures and gender ideologies that are reinforced through media language and imagery. The central problem, therefore, lies in the persistent discursive practices that undermine the visibility, agency, and diversity of Nigerian women in the media, despite their growing roles in society.

Aim and Objectives

The study aims to explore the representations of women in media discourse in Nigeria. The objectives of the study include the followings:

- Media representation contributes to the perpetuation of gender inequalities.
- Gendered stereotypes can lead to discrimination and prejudice.
- Women's voices and perspectives are often silenced or marginalized in media discourse.

Significance of the Study

This study's significance lies in its attempt to expose underlying biases and the impact of media narratives on societal perceptions of women potentially promoting greater awareness.

Literature Review

Discourse and Statement

According to Jenna Crosely (2021), discourse analysis is a method of examining the structure and meaning of connected speech or writing, considering both the linguistic content and the social context in which it occurs. It is a way to understand how meaning is created in different social settings. Zelling Harris (1952), sees discourse analysis as the speech or writing to understand how language works beyond individual sentences. He also explored the relationship between language and culture. Brown and Yule (1983), see discourse analysis as the analysis of language in use, emphasizing the functional aspect of language in use, highlighting how language is used to achieve specific goals and serve various purposes.

Discourse analysis also considers how language enacts social and cultural perspectives and identities. It examines the patterns of language used in different social domains, considering factors like context, power dynamics, and the intentions of speakers. Discourse Analysis (DA) is a broad field of study that draws some of its theories and methods of analysis from disciplines such as linguistics and sociology. Discourse Analysis has provided models and methods of engaging issues that emanate from disciplines such as education, cultural studies, and communication.

Media is defined broadly to include the internet, newspapers, magazines, television, and other mass communication channels. Research indicates that girls as young as age six hold stereotypical images of women significantly influencing their career aspirations (Chambers & Thompson, 2020). Following the Beijing Declaration, UN women launched the global media monitoring project to evaluate the extent of gender inequality in news media. Since 1995, every five years, a research team reports the men-women ratio of news sources worldwide. The most recent result from 2015 identified a gender imbalance pointing at 24% female versus 75% male news source (World Association for Christian Communication WACC, 2015). There was only a slow increase of 7% in women's visibility in the news. The number of women increased the most in newspapers that is, from 16% in 1995 to 26% in 2015. European results hardly differ from the overall pattern. In 2015, there was 25% of women in traditional news media, which was an increase of 9% over the last 20 years. Female actors are underrepresented compared to their male counterparts in general, with 70 to 80% men against 20 to 30% women reported on.

Women are often portrayed in stereotypical ways, reinforcing gendered power dynamics. Media representations can perpetuate negative stereotypes, limiting women's social roles and impacting their self-perception. Additionally, media discourse can contribute to the objectification and sexualization of women, further marginalizing them. This study reveals that persistent patterns of stereotyping and marginalization often reinforce societal power imbalances rather than promoting positive and diverse portrayals. Studies using approaches like critical discourse analysis and feminist discourse analysis, expose how language, visuals, and narrative structures can contribute to this problematic representation.

Example

Objectification and Sexualization

Media often depicts women as primarily sexual objects, reducing them to their physical appearance and neglecting their agency or intellectual capabilities (Campbell, 2000).

Stereotyping

Traditional gender roles and negative stereotypes are frequently reinforced, portraying women as homemakers, emotional or passive in relation to men (Clifford, 2017).

Underrepresentation and Marginalization

Women, particularly those from marginalized groups, are often excluded or underrepresented in leadership roles and diverse narratives, leading to a lack of positive role models (Yemisi, 2019).

The “Bad”, “Mad”, “Sad” Archetypes

Studies have identified recurring characterization of women in media, often labeling them as evil, mentally unstable, or emotionally vulnerable, particularly in the context of gender-based violence (Oloyede, 2020).

Media Influence on Social Perception

The way women are portrayed in the media can shape public perception and influence societal attitudes, perpetuating harmful norms and biases (Temitope, 2013).

Language and Semiotics

Analysis of language use, imagery, and visual elements reveal media constructs and reinforces gendered stereotypes and ideologies such as using terms that highlight their physical appearance or emotional state while down-playing their intellect and capabilities.

Fictional Media

Fictional narratives often portray women in limited and stereotypical roles, perpetuating harmful narratives about gender and relationships using “ideology. Ideologies are representations of aspects of the world which can be shown to contribute to establishing, maintaining, and changing social relations of powers, domination, and explanation” (Fairclough 2003).

Language and Discourse

Language construct can perpetuate social inequalities, including gender inequalities, by reinforcing existing power structures and social norms through the use of language. This is done through various mechanisms like biased word choices, representations of gender roles, and narratives that limit or shape societal perception of gender capabilities (Richardson 2007).

Word Choices

Language often uses gendered terms that categorize individuals based on their gender identity, reinforcing societal norms and stereotypes about the roles and capabilities of men and women. For example, using “man” to refer to leadership

positions points to the idea that men are naturally suited for such roles (Fowler 1991).

Lexical Choices

Words associated with certain genders can promote stereotypes and reinforce power dynamics. For example, using terms like “he or she” to refer to professions often reinforces gendered expectations about roles and responsibilities, as Butler (1990), who emphasized that:

“People do gender rather than have gender”.

Theoretical Frame Work

This study adopts Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) which examines how language and media portrayals construct and reinforce gender stereotypes and power imbalances. CDA explores the relationship between language, ideology and social power, revealing how media narratives perpetuate gender inequality. The study is based on Norman Fairclough’s three proposed analysis stages of discourse which are: text, discourse practice and socio-cultural practice (Darma 2009). According to Alison Bechdel (1985) on the portrayal, participation and representation of women in the news media across 20 years and 114 countries, only 24 percent of the persons heard, read about or seen in newspaper, television and radio news are women.

The representation of women in media is largely portrayed as the pleasure of sexuality and sensuality, confirming gender-based roles and division of labour at home and society, or as innocent victims/violators of social attitudes and mindsets towards gender discrimination. Whereas, men characters are portrayed with confidence, power, and authority, taking leadership and making decisions, or caught in unfavourable circumstances created by one of the women in his life. (Charu Gupta, 2001).

Women have been subjected to not only symbolic but also physical violence (Gill (2007). Violence against women has received increased attention both globally and nationally since the 1970s (Sister 2014). This growing concern is due to the perceived historical inequalities between women and men, and considered as the main hindrance to equity and development. Socio-cultural ideologies including toxic masculinity have hampered this process. Discourses on violence against women are reflections of how patriarchy manifests in daily life. The discourse on violence against women highlights the importance of questioning power and control in a patriarchal society. Arnott & Hope (1970) argue that “violence is nothing more than the most flagrant manifestations of power.”

Van Dijk (1988) explains that the process of discursive reproduction of violence and power involves access to discourse and to a wide range of communication

events. Some studies suggest that Nigerian media, including publications like the *Vanguard*, often portray women in their photographic images. This portrayal can reinforce gender stereotypes, limit women to traditional roles, and contribute to gender discrimination. These representations often focus on women in domestic or stereotypical roles, rather than showcasing their achievements or contributions in their areas.

Methodology

This study uses the Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) framework that analyzes the relationship between language, ideology and social power to examine how language, imagery, and other media elements construct and convey gendered meanings. A variety of media texts including news articles, advertisements, television shows and social media contents were gathered. Data were purposively collected using two Nigerian Newspapers which are *Daily Trust* and *Vanguard* respectively.

Sampling Procedure

Random sampling technique was adopted.

Instrument of Data Collection

The instrument of data collection for the study was code sheet which contained the parameters of analysis.

Data Analysis and Findings

In news reports, women are frequently described through their appearance or emotions rather than their expertise or accomplishments. In advertisements, women are often shown as beautiful objects rather than individuals with agency. By examining the specific ways in which women are represented in media, Critical Discourse Analysis seeks to uncover the underlying power dynamics and ideologies that shape gender relations.

Below is the analysis of the data on the frequency of women representation in media discourse positively or negatively identified.

Table 1. Stereotypical Portrayals

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Stereotypical portrayals	Positively identified	10	10
	Negatively identified	2	1
“Bad woman” Depicted as manipulative, dangerous, or evil	Positively identified	10	10
	Negatively identified	1	1

“Mad woman” Portrayed as irrational, crazy, or unable to control emotions	Positively identified	9	10
	Negatively identified	1	2
“Sad woman” Presented as a victim or oppressed individual	Positively identified	10	8
	Negatively identified	2	2

Table 1 above depicts how frequently the media marginalized women through harmful stereotypes. These findings explore how media constructs perpetuate this representation including the “bad woman”, “mad woman”, and “sad woman” archetypes which can contribute to negative societal perceptions of women.

Table 2. Objectification

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Objectification: Women are often shown as “objects of sexual desire, with an emphasis on their physical appearance”	Positively identified	10	8
	Negatively identified	0	0
Assets	Positively identified	6	6
	Negatively identified	3	2

In table 2 above, women are frequently objectified in the media, being reduced to their physical appearance or sexualized. It is seen that *Daily Trust* and *Vanguard* positively identified with 10 and 8 percentages.

Table 3. Reinforcing Gender Roles

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Subordinate Roles: The frequency placement in subordinate roles often in the background or with limited agency	Positively identified	6	5
	Negatively identified	2	2

The above table shows that *Daily Trust* and *Vanguard* Newspapers placed women in subordinate roles and reinforce traditional gender roles focusing on women roles in the home or family.

Table 4. Domestic Roles

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Domestic Roles: The media often reinforce traditional gender roles by focusing on women's roles in the home and family	Positively identified	8	7
	Negatively identified	3	2

The above table shows how the media frequently depicts women through narrow and restrictive roles, such as housewives, mothers, or beauty icons, neglecting their diverse abilities and contributions which can lead to a limited understanding of women's complexities and potentials, reinforcing traditional gender expectations.

Table 5. Underrepresentation

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Underrepresentation: In position of power or authority both in reality and in media representations	Positively identified	10	10
	Negatively identified	0	0

The table above has shown how women are underrepresented in the media, especially in professional or leadership roles. This can be analyzed by comparing the positive identification and negative identification.

Table 6. Impact on Society

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Negative Self-Perceptions: In self-images or self-esteem and sense of inadequacy (for women)	Positively identified	6	5
	Negatively identified	3	4

The above table shows the perception of the society frequently focuses on the victim and stigmatization.

Table 7. Limited Opportunity

THEME	IDENTIFICATION	DAILY TRUST FREQUENCY	VANGUARD FREQUENCY
Limited Opportunities: The portrayal of women in media can perpetrate stereotypes that limit opportunities for women in various fields	Positively identified	8	7
	Negatively identified	0	0

With the above table, the media often positioned women as passive or subordinate to men, reinforcing the notion of male dominance and female vulnerability.

A critical analysis of women representation in media discourse is crucial for understanding how language and media shape societal perceptions of gender and power. By analyzing media representations, we can identify and challenge harmful stereotypes, and work towards a just and equitable society.

Conclusion

This critical analysis of media discourse reveals how women are frequently positioned in subordinate roles, or characterized by negative tropes, such as the “bad woman,” “mad woman,” or “sad woman”. The analysis highlights how the media perpetuates negative portrayals of women, particularly through news coverage and advertisements, where women are often depicted as passive, sexualized, or solely limited within domestic roles. While progress is being made in some areas, the overall impact of the media on women’s representation continues to be of a significant concern. Despite some progress in recent years, the media often portrays women as objects of desire, reinforcing patriarchal power dynamics, or presents them in limited often negative roles.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Promote Female Role Models:** Highlighting successful and diverse women in various field can inspire future generations and challenge stereotypes.
2. **Challenge Stereotypes:** Media content should actively deconstruct and challenge harmful stereotypes that perpetuate inequalities.
3. **Accurate and Positive Portrayals:** The media should ensure that women are represented in a realistic, positive, and nuanced way, avoiding generalization and tokenism.

4. Address the Paradox: Be mindful of the potential for highlighting challenges faced by women to inadvertently reinforce negative perceptions.

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